

IMPACT ON GLOBAL BEHAVIOURS DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC

DATS 6103 – INDIVIDUAL PROJECT 2 - ARATHI NAIR

THE STUDY

- The objective of this study is to analyze the impact Covid-19 had on people's health and quality of life around the world since the pandemic started and how compliant they have been with COVID-19 safety measures. This analysis gives us an insight into how people have adapted and changed their behaviour as the situation has evolved.
- The data for this study has been sourced from an ongoing global survey conducted by Imperial College London in partnership with YouGov, a global public opinion organisation.
- This survey was conducted across 29 countries with close to 400000 respondents per week and the research data used in this analysis is from April 2020 till October 2020.
- **Data Source:** <https://github.com/YouGov-Data/covid-19-tracker>

- Country
- United Kingdom
 - Australia
 - Brazil
 - Canada
 - China
 - Denmark
 - Finland
 - France
 - Germany
 - Hong Kong
 - India
 - Indonesia
 - Italy
 - Japan
 - Malaysia
 - Mexico
 - Netherlands
 - Norway
 - Philippines
 - Saudi Arabia
 - Singapore
 - South Korea
 - Spain
 - Sweden
 - Taiwan
 - Thailand
 - Vietnam

COUNTRIES SURVEYED

AGE GROUP

NUMBER OF PEOPLE TESTED & TESTED POSITIVE FOR COVID-19

- *Thailand, Saudi Arabia and UAE show a higher number of respondents testing themselves for COVID-19 compared to other countries, which is the key reason for the high percentage of people testing positive in these countries.*
- *While fewer respondents from countries like China, US, India are getting themselves tested when these countries had a significant rise in COVID-19 cases since April. This easily indicates that with fewer people testing, many infections are going undetected.*

COMMON COVID-19 SYMPTOMS

- **Most of the respondents who contracted the virus were asymptomatic.**
- **Dry cough and shortness of breath were the most common symptoms noticed among the people who showed symptoms.**

Covid-19 Symptoms

Covid-19 Symptoms

SELF-ISOLATED POST CONTRACTING THE VIRUS

- Most respondents from Brazil, Indonesia, Saudi Arabia, Thailand, UAE have self-isolated themselves after contracting the virus.

WILLINGNESS TO SELF-ISOLATE IF ADVISED

- Most respondents were willing to self-isolate themselves if they were advised to do so by public health authorities. Spain, UK, Vietnam have the highest positive response.

PERSONAL MEASURES TAKEN TO PREVENT COVID 19

- *A high percentage of people from all countries have used face masks and avoided public areas since the pandemic has started. While the percentage of people working from home and parents avoiding children from sending to schools are relatively more in countries with high COVID-19 cases compared to countries with low COVID-19 cases.*

Avoided Public Transport

Worked From Home

Avoided Letting Children Go To School

LIKELIHOOD OF CONTRACTING THE VIRUS BASED ON PRECAUTIONS TAKEN

- *A significant difference is observed in the number of people who contracted the virus based on the precautions they have taken to prevent contracting the virus. Majority of people that tested positive did not wear a mask or followed strict social distancing.*

TESTING POSITIVE WITH PRE-EXISTING HEALTH CONDITIONS

- *All groups are almost equally vulnerable to contracting the coronavirus. A slightly higher percentage of people with Multiple Sclerosis, HIV, Cancer, Fibrosis have tested positive.*

GOVERNMENT RESPONSE TO COVID-19

- Respondents from Vietnam and Malaysia strongly believe that their government has taken effective response measures and successfully managed the pandemic. Whereas the respondents from United States and Japan on the other hand are dissatisfied with their government's handling of the virus outbreak.**

RANKING HAPPINESS LEVEL - APRIL 2020 TO OCTOBER 2020

- The average happiness ranked by all countries were very low in the month of April, which was the beginning of the pandemic. Over the months respondents have ranked their happiness level higher, especially in countries like Netherlands, Finland, Denmark and Mexico with an average of 6 to 7 points on a 0 - 10 happiness index scale.

FEAR OF COVID -19

- ***Indonesia, Malaysia, Vietnam showed highest fear of contracting the coronavirus and falling ill, while countries like Finland, Germany, Netherlands showed lowest stress and anxiety levels.***

CONCLUSION

- Large number of people have taken more preventive measures like maintaining personal hygiene, physical distancing, and wearing a mask when going out in public, to help protect themselves and to reduce the chances of spreading the infection to others
- The number of people testing in many countries are still very low which can lead to many cases to go undetected and making it difficult to control the spread of the virus
- Coronavirus outbreak has caused life satisfaction to fall sharply in most countries, especially in countries that are largely affected by the pandemic.

THANK YOU

